

ESSENTIAL ONLINE PLATFORMS FOR GRAPHIC DESIGNERS

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Abstract. This article analyzes a collection of the most important online platforms for graphic designers. Information was provided about Adobe Creative Cloud, Canva, Figma, Behance, Dribbble, 99designs, Designhill and Piktochart platforms. These platforms provide many opportunities for interaction, community engagement, design and portfolio creation. All of them also allow graphic designers to facilitate their work, develop and provide new creations. This platform is one of the most important resources for graphic designers' portfolios, jobs and public relations indicators.

Key words. platforms, adobe creative cloud, canva, figma, behance, dribbble, 99designs, designhill, Piktochart, Freepik, Pinterest, Google Fonts, BestFonts.pro, Shutterstock, shapeFactory.

Аннотация. В этой статье будет проанализирована коллекция самых важных онлайн-платформ для графических дизайнеров. Поддерживаются платформы Adobe Creative Cloud, Canva, Figma, Behance, Dribbble, 99designs, Designhill и Piktochart. Эти платформы предоставляют множество возможностей для взаимодействия, общественной работы, дизайна и создания портфолио. Все они также позволяют графическим дизайнерам облегчать, развивать и вносить новшества в свою работу. Эта платформа является одним из наиболее важных ресурсов для портфолио графического дизайнера, показателей работы и связей с общественностью.

Ключевые слова. платформы, adobe creative cloud, canva, figma, behance, dribbble, 99designs, designhill, Piktochart, Freepik, Pinterest, Google Fonts, BestFonts.pro, Shutterstock, ShapeFactory.

Online platforms for graphic designers help to facilitate, develop and stay in touch with their work. These platforms also allow them to showcase their

designs, get feedback and provide new creations. The following are some of the most important online platforms for graphic designers:

Adobe Creative Cloud - This is a platform includes Adobe Illustrator, Photoshop, InDesign, Premiere Pro and many other design tools. These programs are suitable for graphic design, image, illustration, video editing and many other design tasks. Adobe Creative Cloud provides a private cloud service for users to store their private files.

Canva - This is a platform allows users to work with many templates for graphic design, visual information and other services. This platform allows you to create high-quality templates and additional views for your designs.

Figma - This is a platform that allows collaboration, prototyping and editing of public works. This platform is suitable for all types of image, graphic design, UI/UX design and many other design tasks. Figma provides users with many features to make their community work more organized and efficient.

Behance - This is a platform features graphic design, image, illustration and many other design tasks. This platform includes creating an online portfolio for their designs and public works.

Dribbble - This is a community platform that allows graphic designers to submit their designs, provide feedback, and connect with other designers. This platform provides designers with new creations and benchmarks.

99designs - This is a platform that helps designers find work. Users can make changes to their projects to create additional views. This platform provides direct communication between designers and customers.

Designhill - This is a platform that helps you sell your design with stealth. Users can choose from several design options to create. This platform allows designers to connect with clients who receive additional information, as well as find award-winning work.

Piktochart - This is a platform that helps you create visual information. Users can use templates or create their own designs. This platform allows you to create infographics, maps, charts and other visual information. Piktochart provides a user-friendly and intuitive interface.

Freepik - This is a website dedicated to images. The content produced and distributed by the online platform includes photographs, illustrations and vector images. The platform distributes its content under a freemium model, meaning users can access a large portion of the content for free. But in addition, access to more exclusive resources, subscriptions with benefits that are not applicable to used content can be purchased.

Pinterest – This is a social Internet service that allows users to add images online, put them into themed collections, and share them with other users. Pinterest is especially popular among women because of the artistic design of the site. As of November 30, 2016, the site ranks 50th in the alexa.com ranking.

Google Fonts - This is a computer font and web font service owned by Google. This includes free and open source font families, an interactive web catalog for library browsing, CSS, and an API for using fonts via Android. Popular fonts in the Google Fonts library include Roboto, Open Sans, Lato, Oswald, Montserrat, Source Sans Pro, and Raleway.

BestFonts.pro – This is where you can download fonts for free and then use them on your website or install them on MacOS and Windows. It is also easy to connect the kits presented on the portal to Photoshop, Figma and Sketch or Adobe InDesign editors for typing. For your convenience, headphones are divided into categories with quick selection filters.

Shutterstock – This is an American company that provides photo, video, music and editing tools. The headquarters of the company is located in New York. Founded in 2003 by programmer and photographer John Oringer. As of 2023, its library contains more than 440 million images, as well as royalty-free vectors and images, video clips and music.

ShapeFactory - This is a set of design tools built by designers for everyone. It's a place for product enthusiasts to share and learn about the latest mobile apps, websites, hardware projects, and tech creations.

Summary

Although the mentioned platforms are the most necessary giant platforms for graphic designers, they are only assistants for designers, i.e. platforms that speed up the designer's work and help to create a real work of art. An experienced designer can make a good income independently using these platforms if he knows how to use

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